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Deliverable 3.6 Report describing key enabling drivers of new value chains

Closing the gap between fork and farm for circular nutrient flows

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D3.6 – Report describing key enabling drivers of new value chains

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Acronyms

AGL	Agualytics
AXA	Axaragua
BREEAM	Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method
BioA	Bioazul
CE	Circular Economy
CO2	Carbon Dioxide
CET	Cetaqua
EU	European Union
ESG	Environmental, Social, and Governance
GB	Gotland Bryggeri
GE	Goldeimer
KWB	Kreiswerke Barnim
R&D	Research & Development
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals
ROI	Return on Investment
S360	Sanitation360
SFT	Smart Fertigation Tool
SLU	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
T3.1	Task 3.1
T3.4	Task 3.4
TD	Touch Down Gotland
VH	Vagtshoff Farm
VN	VunaNexus
WP	Work Package
WWTP	Wastewater Treatment Plant

1 Executive Summary

This deliverable explores how circular business models aimed at closing the nutrient loop between urban and rural environments are fostering the emergence of new, interdependent value chains that stand in contrast to traditional linear approaches. These circular business models are accompanied by novel activities and collaborative structures that demand close coordination and partnership across all involved stakeholders.

This deliverable (3.6) specifically examines the key enabling drivers that support the realisation of new circular value chains to facilitate the treatment of waste as a resource, reintegrating it into nutrient cycles, rather than allowing it to be wasted.

The investigation applied a qualitative approach, primarily based on 11 in-depth interviews with value chain actors across the three pilot regions participating in P2Green. Respectively, the Gotland region, the North German Plain and Axarquia pilot region. The analysis integrated both deductive insights from existing research and inductive findings from empirical data, enabling a balanced and comprehensive understanding of the enabling conditions for circular business model development. Moreover, this deliverable builds on earlier value chain mapping and collaborative workshops.

By analysing the factors that motivate, incentivise, and support organisations in engaging in nutrient-focused circular economy (CE) initiatives, three overarching categories of key enabling drivers were identified across the P2Green pilot regions: (1) systemic and regulatory drivers, (2) market drivers, and (3) operational and organisational drivers.

Key findings highlight shared challenges across all pilot regions, particularly the difficulty of commercialising circular solutions within sectors embedded in linear systems—such as wastewater treatment, fertiliser production, and conventional agriculture. Under systemic and regulatory drivers, critical enabling conditions include: supportive and harmonised policies across governance levels, financial support to bridge cost gaps, infrastructure investment, and third-party certification to build public trust in biobased fertilisers.

Market drivers focus on raising public awareness, the need for price competitiveness, and increasing environmental awareness. To gain traction, circular products must not only meet sustainability criteria but also be economically viable and aligned with customer expectations. On the operational and organisational level, success hinges on adaptable product design, maturing technology, strategic partnerships, and the presence of key individuals who champion innovation and collaboration.

Municipalities also play a pivotal enabling role by fostering public-private collaboration and facilitating regulatory navigation, particularly for smaller or emerging stakeholders.

The findings inform both pilot-specific business models and broader strategic recommendations.

The report concludes that enabling drivers for circular value chains differ fundamentally from those underpinning linear systems. Realising circularity requires coordinated political action, targeted legislation, financial support, and robust cross-sector collaboration to create the systemic change necessary for adopting the proposed circular business models. The generalisable findings presented in this deliverable directly inform the upscaling blueprint in Work Package 5 (WP5): “Scaling the Impact” and serve as a knowledge foundation for supporting the development of similar circular value chains across the European Union (EU).

2 Introduction

The fertiliser industry has traditionally been characterised as a conservative and change-resistant sector. This is largely due to the long-standing effectiveness of conventional products and the continued low cost of key raw materials, such as phosphate rock (De Boer et al., 2018). This structural rigidity presents significant challenges for the transition towards a CE, particularly when it comes to recycling nutrients. Recycling nutrients into fertiliser remains a niche practice within a dominant regime that still favours conventional, linear, and emission-intensive fertiliser production (Aliahmad et al., 2023).

At the same time, growing global populations are placing increasing pressure on food and clean water supplies, which in turn heightens energy demand and deepens reliance on finite natural resources. Our prevailing economic model is predominantly linear, where the accelerated extraction of key raw materials, such as phosphate rock, not only depletes global reserves but also contributes significantly to environmental degradation (Chojnacka, Moustakas, & Witek-Krowiak, 2020).

Mineral fertiliser production uses a substantial amount of energy and relies heavily on fossil fuels, as exemplified by the Haber Bosch process for nitrogen fertilisers, as well as on materials sourced from fossil deposits like phosphate rock (Chojnacka et al., 2020). Although these practices have historically supported food security for a growing global population (Zhang et al., 2019), its disadvantages have driven interest in replacing mineral fertilisers with biobased alternatives. In fact, manufacturing and transporting these mineral fertilisers accounts for roughly 2% of the world's total energy use (Chojnacka et al., 2020).

Transitioning from a fossil fuel based, linear system to a CE involves recovering nutrients from waste streams and substituting traditional mineral fertilisers with biobased options (Chojnacka et al., 2020). In response to the environmental challenges with the current fertiliser schemes and security of supply, the European Commission has embraced CE principles that emphasises the recovery of materials and systems where vital nutrients are recycled to a much greater extent instead of relying on non-renewable resources/nutrients (European Commission, 2017). The vision of a closed loop in fertiliser production is supported by both the EU and the European Industrial Organisation of Fertilisers (Chojnacka et al., 2020). Through the EU strategy 'Farm to Fork' under the European Green Deal, the EU aims to cut nutrient losses by 50 per cent and reduce fertiliser use by at least 20 per cent by 2030 (European Commission, n.d.).

Biobased fertilisers are designed to lessen the EU's dependence on imported mineral fertilisers by reclaiming nutrients from nutrient rich waste streams. However, implementing these alternatives is complex and calls for effective policies to streamline their production and use. Several challenges remain, including the fact that some biobased products have yet to match the productivity of chemical fertilisers. Issues such as high transportation costs, technological hurdles, regulatory and certification

requirements, field validation trials, scalability and social acceptance still need to be overcome. Farmers, in particular, are concerned about the mineralisation and hygienisation processes and expect prices to be competitive with those of chemical fertilisers, given their sensitivity to cost (Kurniawati et al., 2023). Moreover, public awareness regarding challenges related to nutrients is low, as phosphorus stands as an invisible concern in society (De Boer et al., 2018).

Using recovered byproducts in this way is essentially an application of CE principles. It is anticipated that biowaste could eventually replace up to 30 per cent of the fertilisers currently in use (Chojnacka et al., 2020). The utilisation of sanitary waste, as the object of investigation in the P2Green project, stands as a distinct nutrient recycling opportunity.

To foster a circular transition, nutrient recycling innovations must be cultivated, supported, and diffused, so in time, the circular solutions become part of the established mainstream market (Hasler, Olf, Omta, & Bröring, 2016).

By investigating the mechanisms necessary for driving these novel nutrient recycling solutions, this deliverable contributes to identifying the conditions necessary for enabling and scaling the fertiliser solutions and accelerating the shift toward a more circular and sustainable nutrient economy.

2.1 Overview and Objectives of Deliverable 3.6

This deliverable under work package 3 “*Supporting the Transition*” aims to investigate and identify which key enabling drivers exist in the new value chains that support circular solutions with the objective to understand how these drivers facilitate partnerships that enforce nutrient loops.

To achieve this, the task compares the drivers present in the circular value chains with those found in traditional, linear systems. This is accomplished by analysing data from the three P2Green pilot regions, where interviews with each partner in the pilots have been conducted. These interviews, based on an appreciative inquiry approach, explore the collaborations in circular value chains and which key enabling drivers are identified by the pilots. The insights obtained not only benefit the pilot regions but also provide valuable knowledge for organisations across the EU. Moreover, the findings will contribute to the development of an upscaling blueprint in WP5, moving the project from subjective, case-specific observations to broader, general conclusions regarding the drivers that enable successful nutrient recycling projects.

The aim of this report is to transition from subjective observations to more general conclusions, therefore the focus will be on insights that are consistent across the different pilot regions. However, relevant patterns specific to individual pilots that may apply to other circular systems will also be highlighted. Finally, the main findings of the analysis will be presented in the conclusion.

3 Methodology

In this section the overall methodology for the deliverable is outlined, including data collection approach and process as well as data analysis.

3.1 Data Collection

3.1.1 Appreciative Inquiry

The qualitative data collection and analysis in the report takes its starting point from an appreciative inquiry point. This is an approach that emphasises the positive instead of the negative (Nel & Govender, 2019) in a development process. Utilising an appreciative inquiry approach to collect data is a way to discover and unfold the strengths, successes and aspirations of the individuals or groups to base future development on these positive features (Brailas, 2025). Rather than concentrating on problems or deficiencies, appreciative inquiry is founded on the principle that something works and focuses on identifying what is good and exploring ways to enable and amplify these positive elements.

By integrating these principles, the appreciative inquiry approach fosters a constructive and forward-thinking process, which helps to identify the key enabling drivers of circular value chains.

3.1.2 Desk Research

In the initial phase of the investigation, relevant literature on CE, including circular business models and circular supply chains, was reviewed to establish an understanding of theoretical concepts and the pre-existing body of literature on linear and circular value chains.

To understand the theoretical concepts of circular supply chains, the Ellen MacArthur Foundation was a key reference, offering insights into CE value chains and frameworks. The Ellen MacArthur Foundation is a non-profit organisation dedicated to accelerating the transition to a circular economy, by collaborating with academia, business, policymakers and institutions to develop and promote CE principles. Furthermore, distinct desk research was conducted to review literature and build a knowledge-foundation regarding sector-specific conditions, and drivers and barriers for fertiliser and nutrient recycling.

3.1.3 In-depth interviews

To obtain an in-depth understanding of the key enabling drivers identified in the pilot regions, it was required that a minimum of 3 interviews were conducted in each pilot region. Motivated by the aim of gaining nuanced, individual insights into each partner's perspectives, 11 semi-structured interviews were conducted composed of a single interview conducted with each partner. The in-depth interviews focused on investigating key enabling drivers for successful collaboration in circular value chains and how their

collaboration in a circular business model differs from collaboration in a linear business model. The semi-structured interview is a qualitative research approach that methodically is placed between a regular conversation and a questionnaire (Albaret & Deas, 2023). By integrating a predefined set of open questions, it provides flexibility for the interviewer to explore specific topics that might occur (ibid.). Given the strong link between key enabling drivers and business model development (D3.1), much of the data collected through Task 3.1 (T3.1) also served as a knowledge foundation for the development of this deliverable. Thus, the in-depth group interviews related to identification of value creation flows for T3.1, prior to the 11 individual semi-structured interviews, revealed key insights into both drivers and barriers of circular value chain collaborations.

Prior to each round of data collection, interview guides were conducted to ensure the approach of the appreciative inquiry was followed and that the relevant topics and questions were discussed. The 11 in-depth interviews with consortium partners were conducted with participation from the following partners:

- **Gotland pilot region** (Sweden): Sanitation360 (S360), Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU), Gotland Bryggeri (GB), Touch Down Gotland (TD) (S360 and SLU interview was conducted in a single session)
- **North German Plain** (Germany): VunaNexus (VN), Goldeimer (GE), Kreiswerke Barnim (KWB)
- **Region of Axarquía** (Spain): Bioazul (BioA), TROPS, Axaragua (AXA), Agualytics (AGL), Cetaqua (CET)

3.2 Driver Categories

In this deliverable, the key enabling drivers are defined as the primary factors that motivate, create incentives for, or support organisations in participating in CE initiatives or implementing circular business models.

Furthermore, several barriers that prevent business models from scaling have consistently emerged throughout the data collection sessions. These barriers have been considered essential to include in the analysis since key enabling drivers may mitigate or remove them, meaning that the barriers and drivers are interconnected.

To systematically gain insights into these common drivers, the analysis is structured around three main categories of drivers which was identified as common enabling driver categories across the pilots respectively *systemic and regulatory drivers*, *market drivers*, and *operational and organisational drivers*.

Firstly, the *systemic and regulatory drivers* refer to policies, regulations, legislation, and overall governmental incentives. These incentives are introduced at state or supra-state levels and are directly or indirectly influencing the feasibility and scalability of circular business models. For instance, lack of financial support from governments can hinder the interest of implementing CE strategies (Govindan et al., 2018). While regulations

and incentives can act as both drivers and barriers, this investigation focuses on their positive effects in driving circular economic initiatives. E.g. governments can use financial tools such as subsidies and supportive taxation to leverage businesses adopting circular solutions and lower the risks in establishing circular businesses (Tura et al., 2019). These financial tools allocate resources in favour of biobased fertilisers which can help increase their competitiveness. Beyond direct financial support, governments can implement market regulations that reduce the competitive advantage of mineral fertilisers. For example, by introducing taxes or tariffs that discourage the use of synthetic fertilisers, regulatory bodies can help create a more level playing field for biobased alternatives, thereby enhancing their cost competitiveness.

Turning to *the market drivers*, these concerns the mechanisms that fosters the ability of the biobased fertiliser products to compete on market terms ensure an actual demand for the fertilisers (Geissdoerfer et al., 2023). Among others, this involves increased sustainability awareness, recognition of avoided costs and public acceptance of crops grown from reclaimed water and/or fertilisers produced with nutrients from human sanitary waste.

The third driver encompasses *operational and organisational drivers*. These drivers include factors such as collaboration, knowledge sharing, and technological advancements/development that affect the implementation and effective operation of circular systems (Geissdoerfer et al., 2023) (Tura et al., 2019) (Govindan et al., 2018). Overall, they relate to how circular business models are organised collaboratively, how participation in circular value chains influences company capabilities, and how technological development influence scalability of the solutions.

By structuring the data analysis around these three categories of drivers, the key enabling factors shared across the pilot regions have been systematically identified through the 11 interviews conducted with pilot partners. This approach provides a clear framework for understanding how systemic, market, and operational drivers collectively contribute to the success of circular nutrient recycling initiatives.

3.3 Data Analysis

The method of thematic analysis was applied to identify, analyse and report the most important insights for each pilot. The interviews conducted were transcribed, coded and analysed separately, with a subsequent comparative analysis of the insights that were obtained. In line with Braun et al. (2022) the first part of the analysis involved generation of initial codes; assigning meaning and short classifications to the quotes from the interviews.

To identify the most important overall insights, codes were classified both deductively and inductively. In relation to the deductive approach, a predefined list of themes had been created from building on the methodology from the interview-guide and relevant literature. Each theme was separated into subthemes such as drivers of collaboration,

social acceptance, market competition. This allowed codes to be matched with the most appropriate sub-theme and create a strong link across the pilot regions.

Different codes were also inductively developed with grounding in the data rather than the predefined themes. This has enabled unexpected insights to be identified and reduced the likelihood of important insights to be overlooked. Such codes were structured into preliminary sub-themes that were refined and named to represent the story of the codes (Braun et al., 2022).

The coding of each semi-structured interview provided an overview of the key enabling drivers for pilot region partners. Following the initial coding, patterns across the pilot region partners became apparent, while a comparative analysis was conducted to reveal key enabling drivers at a broader level considering all three pilot regions.

4 Theory

This section explores the theoretical concepts of value chains drawing on the understandings of the Ellen MacArthur Foundation. The section introduces both traditional value chains and circular value chains and how these are emphasising collaboration and networking across partners.

4.1 Value Chains of P2Green – a Network and Orchestration Perspective

Traditionally, the value chain describes the full range of activities to bring a product from its conception to end use and beyond, either contained within a single organisation or divided among different organisations (Gereffi et al., 2019).

However, the interdependent nature of the circular value chains in P2Green requires a perspective of value chains as orchestrated networks containing a series of activities that different organisations engage in (Zucchella et al., 2018) to perform the traditional value chain activities of design, production, marketing, delivery, and support of the products or services offered for customers (Porter, 2008). The perspective of value chains as networks entails that both nodes (companies) and their specific threads (relationships), possess resources and knowledge, in which orchestration can facilitate exchanges between the organisations. (Håkansson et al., 2002; Zucchella et al., 2018). In P2Green, this type of orchestration plays a vital role for development, implementation and engagement in the network with different technology providers, research institutions, cooperatives, and other stakeholders interacting across the circular value chain.

The interdependencies created through collaborations are facilitated by organisations characterised as ‘innovation champions’ who deeply embedded in the network (Zucchella et al., 2018). Such ‘innovation champions’ are present in all value chains represented in the pilot regions by the different technology providers. The ability to recognise and manage the linkages between the different value creating activities performed by the collaborating partners is what potentially yields competitive advantages – the fundamental basis of above-average performance in the long run (Porter, 2008).

4.2 Collaborating in Circular Value Chains

CE is a concept in which waste does not exist. In a CE all materials, whether being technical or, as in the case of P2Green, biological, are recovered and recycled. This means that the traditional way of conducting business, which is often referred to as the linear economy due to its take-make-dispose way of functioning, must be fundamentally reimaged.

In a CE, products and materials that would otherwise have been considered to be waste, are kept in loop, for example through recover or recycling. Achieving this requires a reconfiguration of the value chains that form the basis of products and services, as well as the establishment of partnerships with stakeholders willing to

challenge the status quo and transform waste into valuable resources. The circular value chains must encompass the activities that maximises the value of a product or a service, just as the traditional value chains.

According to the Ellen MacArthur Foundation, creating circular value chains requires not only reconfiguration of the value chain but also relies heavily on collaboration with and between the partners that collaborate in the value chains (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2023). The partners are interdependent and interconnected of one another (ibid) and opposite to the tradition value chains, the customers constitute a pivotal role in the value chain because the customers are the ones to supply the goods and materials to be recovered or recycled.

A successful collaboration between actors in the value chain is expected to facilitate the sourcing of material inputs to produce new goods (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2023).

Unlike linear resource flows in traditional value chains, the exchange of materials and resources in circular value chains occurs through multidirectional flows, fostering new partnerships and innovative ways of engaging with other system actors. These multidirectional flows demand traceability and transparency, which, in turn, enhance the resilience and robustness of the value chains (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2023). Through traceability and transparency, trust among the collaborating partners is enhanced and may encourage more transformational collaboration in the value chains (ibid.)

As such, achieving a circular value chain requires mutual trust, clear roles, reciprocity, transparency and a shared vision. These elements foster shared solutions that benefit all parties and create interdependency (Hernandez Marquina et al., 2024), unlike the more isolated, transactional relationships seen in linear supply chains. The ideal collaborative circular supply chain ensures that all partners benefit, perhaps not equally, but where no one loses (Serebitskiy, 2021). Unlike in linear models, where the focus is often on cost minimisation without considering broader systemic impacts for the surrounding ecosystem outside of the individual organisation.

Collaboration can further be enhanced by engaging both upstream and downstream partners to create closed-loop systems, implementing circular procurement requirements, and jointly addressing consumer-related barriers to the CE. Establishing partnerships across the value chain allows businesses to co-develop circular solutions, such as designing products or takeback systems with material providers and manufacturers, fostering reciprocity. To this end, transparency plays a crucial role, including sharing data, using supply chain traceability, and providing clear product information to customers, practices that are often lacking in linear models (Gomes et al., 2024).

5 Introduction to the Pilots

The P2Green three pilot regions consist of the Gotland region (Sweden), the North German Plain (Germany) and the region of Axarquía (Spain). All three pilot regions aim to recover and recycle urine or faeces to fertiliser or compost (P2Green, 2023).

In the Gotland region, urine is collected and distributed from sanitation facilities at events, festivals and public venues and converted into pellet fertilisers. The partners engaged in the business model consists of the pilot coordinator S360, the tech-developer SLU, TD, a toilet rental company and finally GB, a Gotlandic brewery (ibid.).

In the North German Plain, two distinct business models are implemented, focusing on the production of fertiliser and compost from separate sources: urine and faeces. Dry toilet matter is collected and processed into nutrient-rich compost by GE, while urine is treated by VN and used to produce a liquid fertiliser under the well-established brand Aurin. Both solutions, the fertiliser and compost are being used for field trials at VH under P2Green. Currently, the North German Plain pilot is inhibited by national legislation that does not allow their products to be marketed (ibid.).

The pilot region in the Axarquía province of Spain, is utilising wastewater from the municipal Wastewater Treatment Plant (WWTP) to fertigate (irrigate and fertilise) farmland in the region. BioA is the project coordinator and provides the treatment technology of the reclaimed water. The reclaimed water is used to fertigate avocados and mango crops currently facilitated by TROPS, a cooperative representing the farmers.

If needed, the reclaimed water can be supplemented with additional fertiliser or diluted with fresh water, all managed through the Smart Fertigation Tool (SFT) provided by AGL. This tool monitors soil nutrient levels to ensure the precise delivery of water and nutrients according to crop needs. Finally, CET a water research centre is contributing with expertise of monitoring and assessing the effectiveness of the water reclamation process (ibid).

6 Key Enabling Drivers

This section assesses the specific key enabling drivers identified in each of the pilot regions, structured across the three driver categories: systemic and regulatory drivers, market drivers, and operational and organisational drivers. The pilot-specific drivers have been organised into a comparative table to provide an overview and allow for cross-pilot comparison of the most significant enabling drivers. The key enabling drivers include both existing and anticipated factors identified by the pilot region partners that support or are expected to support the entry and scaling of the circular value chains.

The purpose of this table is twofold: firstly, it serves as a tool for identifying similarities and differences in the key enabling drivers across the pilots. Secondly, it allows for a more general understanding of which drivers are essential for circular business models within nutrient recycling. The table presents short, synthesised points derived from the pilot interviews and is structured as follows:

Table 1: Key enabling drivers mentioned in pilot interviews

	La Axarquía region, (Spain)	Gotland Region (Sweden)	The North German Plain (Germany)
Systemic & Regulatory drivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear and supporting legislative frameworks • Emergence of new water strategies, nationally and on a municipal level • Economic governmental support – financial aid to support viability and enabling cost competitiveness of reclaimed water • Enabling water tariff frameworks supporting the use of reclaimed water and making it price competitive 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revisions in sanitary management regulation • Streamline municipal regulation regarding collection • Economic governmental support internalising external costs • R&D funding mechanisms like the P2Green project • Green Certifications with focus on sanitation • Third party certification of fertilisers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enabling legal frameworks: legalising nutrient recycling solutions on the market • Economic governmental support to reach price competitiveness (subsidies, CO₂ taxes and avoided costs payments) • Infrastructure investments to support decentralised sanitation solutions • Close collaboration with the municipality on tests

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An increase in discharge taxes and fines for nutrient pollution to waterways • Subsidies for the use of reclaimed water • Promoting tertiary treatment facilities in WWTP • Regional investments in piping infrastructure • Securing easy access to legal permits for farmers wanting to use reclaimed water • Research and Development (R&D) funding mechanisms like the P2Green project 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • R&D funding mechanisms like the P2Green project
<p>Market drivers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User acceptance of reclaimed water / public awareness campaigns • Official label to underscore the reduced environmental and water footprint of agricultural produce • Increased price of well water 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognition of avoided costs for treatment of urine in WWTPs and CO₂ reductions in fertilisers • Customer awareness about the potential of urine as fertiliser and the challenges in the current system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognition of avoided costs of treatment in WWTPs • Third party certification of fertilisers and compost

<p>Operational and organisational drivers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partnerships with public authorities, agrochemical companies, or industry groups • Close collaborations in the circular partnership with mutual interests • Adaptability of the solution - flexibility to suit different farm types and crops • Need for technology maturation • Knowledge sharing exchange of expertise to drive innovation and learn from each other's challenges • Key individuals driving progress in the pilot 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration with the municipality • Strong collaboration among partners and operational control over the value chain • R&D investments in technology to further maturity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • R&D investments in technology ensuring high quality products
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As shown in **Table 1**, systemic and regulatory drivers represent the most dominant driver category across the pilots. This is especially evident in the North German Plain and the Axarquia pilot region, where drivers related to public funding, regulatory support, and infrastructure development play a crucial role. The market drivers are also well-represented, particularly in the Gotland region, where factors such as consumer acceptance and price competitiveness are key. Finally, the operational and organisational drivers are prominent in the Axarquia pilot region, where collaboration between stakeholders and technological adaptability are needed to scale the solution.

In the next section, the analysis will dive deeper into each driver category, examining how the identified drivers are distributed across the pilos and to what extent they are shared or unique. The aim is to move from pilot-specific and context-dependent insights to more general conclusions about which key enabling drivers are crucial for circular business models within nutrient recycling. By shifting the focus from individual pilot data to a consolidated analysis of the findings, this approach aims to better understand the

systemic, market, and operational conditions that are essential for enabling circular innovation to scale and become competitive in the mainstream market.

6.1 Systemic & Regulatory Drivers

Diving into the systemic and regulatory drivers, the key enabling drivers identified across the three pilots are a broad need for governmental support and an enabling regulatory framework.

The identified key enabling drivers on a systemic and regulatory level includes:

- Enabling regulatory frameworks and legislation across governance levels
- Supportive government funding - subsidies, grants, or tax incentives to bridge cost gaps
- Municipalities fostering and facilitating collaboration across industries and public institutions

6.1.1 Changes of Regulatory Frameworks and Legislation

Across all three pilot regions, changes of regulatory frameworks and legislation is a crucial driver to enable self-sustaining nutrient recycling value chains. A common challenge across the three pilot regions is a lack of supportive legislation towards nutrient recycling practices. The three pilot regions are facing different challenges, leading to different key enabling drivers being relevant to address.

In the Gotland region, the differing interpretations of the legislative framework are significantly hindering the scaling of nutrient recycling value chains. This issue arises because municipalities own the waste fraction that covers human sanitary waste and are responsible for its management. However, since it concerns an EU-level Directive it highly depends on the local interpretations undertaken by the municipalities. Therefore, a key enabling driver in this relation is initiating and maintaining a strong relationship with the municipality to ensure favourable local interpretation of the legislation.

Additionally, to advance nutrient recycling practices and foster collaboration between municipalities and private actors in the Gotland region, it is essential to streamline the legislative framework. Further, as emphasised by Case et al. (2017), suggesting that a unified regulatory system for synthetic and biobased fertilisers is needed to increase the attractiveness of biobased fertilisers. This unified system would provide clear guidelines and standards, making it easier for farmers to adopt biobased fertilisers. Additionally, public strategies for building a resilient food system and in extension of this, investigating possible sources of nutrients for agriculture that are essential to support nutrient recycling practices.

In The North German Plain, the most pressing challenge is regulatory since current legislation does not permit nutrient recycling from human excreta. Existing legislation that aims to preserve the conventional system, poses a significant barrier and current policies create a system where human excreta are not assessed as valuable. As a

result, regulatory approval is a prerequisite before the products can be brought to market. From experience the current EU regulations leaves a lot of grey areas for member states to interpret what is possible and what is not. This calls for a unified framework across the EU, that expressively states which types of fertilisers are allowed, to be established.

Consequently, the pilot solution cannot be scaled until these regulatory barriers are addressed. The German government plays a crucial role in both legalising and promoting decentralised sanitation solutions, particularly in remote areas where traditional sewage infrastructure is either unfeasible or prohibitively expensive.

Once a supportive legal framework is in place, opportunities exist to scale the North German Plain, especially in the remote regions, as well as in other areas that are not connected to centralised sewage systems. These locations are well-suited for the decentralised solution developed by the North German Plain. However, successful diffusion of such circular innovations depends on proactive government involvement, not only in enabling legislation but also in driving the promotion and implementation of decentralised systems to ensure equitable access to more sustainable sanitation services across Germany.

In Spain, the government needs to address the issue of depleted water reserves by enacting legislation that disincentivize the current consumption of well-water for irrigation. This can be achieved by creating favourable conditions for companies offering reclaimed water solutions and to invest in infrastructure to meet regional water demands. One essential driver in this relation is the development of new water strategies, already implemented by some Spanish municipalities to mitigate the effects of water shortages by considering alternative sources of irrigation for agriculture and public green areas. Similarly, both national and EU legislation, such as the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive, the Regulation on Water Reuse (Reg. EU 2020/741), which enables water reuse from wastewater, and Spain's Royal Decree 1085/2024 enabling water reuse for irrigation, play a critical role in promoting the adoption of water reuse for irrigation.

Thus, to enable the effective use of alternative sources of water for irrigation, the Spanish government must develop practices and tariffs that promote more sustainable water management practices to ensure long-term water security, such as reducing the time it takes to obtain licenses.

In all three pilot regions, active government support is essential to establish favourable regulatory frameworks and legislation that make nutrient recycling practices a viable business case. This includes creating incentives for companies to engage in and develop their circular value chains. At present, a framework for the development of the nutrient recycling industry is lacking across these regions. However, the establishment of supportive regulatory structures is critical to ensuring the successful, large-scale implementation of circular technologies in all pilot areas.

6.1.2 Government Funding

A fundamental challenge across all three pilot regions is the difficulty these pilots face in competing with conventional products, primarily due to the lack of infrastructure and significant price disparities, which hinder the scalability of the solutions. In this context, it is evident that a central driver for all three circular business models is the need for government intervention, particularly through public funding, to further promote and support the expansion of these circular initiatives.

For all three pilot regions, a key enabling driver to ensure market penetration and customer adoption is the price competitiveness of their products compared to conventional products. Achieving price competitiveness is essential to provide an economic incentive for potential customers, allowing the circular businesses to capture a larger market share. External factors, such as rising energy and mineral fertiliser prices driven by geopolitical situations, particularly impact the Gotland region. These factors have heightened the need for alternative solutions to mineral fertilisers. If biobased fertilisers can offer both competitive pricing and reduced exposure to geopolitical uncertainties, it would present a significant advantage to potential customers.

Policymakers play a critical role in supporting price competitiveness by creating favourable economic conditions, including subsidies, tax incentives, and grants for businesses producing circular products to reduce the price gap between conventional and circular solutions.

Achieving price competitiveness, especially in the Gotland region and the North German Plain region - which reduces the need for removal of nutrients in WWTP - may be possible by recognising the cost savings from reduced nutrient removal in wastewater treatment plants, CO₂ emissions and nutrient pollution. A key enabling factor is for public utilities and municipalities to acknowledge both the financial and environmental benefits of decreasing reliance on conventional WWTP processes and mineral fertilisers. This could involve compensating for avoided treatment costs and assigning a monetary value to CO₂ emissions and nutrient discharges into water bodies, thereby internalising the external costs of current sanitation and fertiliser practices.

These factors, provide a rationale for financial governmental support, and will help ensure that biobased fertilisers in both the North German Plain and the Gotland region can compete effectively with mineral fertilisers in terms of price. Being paid by public authorities to remove nitrogen and phosphorous from wastewater is an essential step of becoming a standard part of the wastewater infrastructure, while reaching price competitiveness will contribute to scaling of the technologies which enable to grow the fertiliser supply in parallel.

In the Axarquia pilot region, price competitiveness is also a vital element for the success of the business model. Farmers have expressed willingness to adopt reclaimed water if it leads to cost reductions in their operations. However, the current low cost of well

water makes it economically unfeasible for farmers to switch to reclaimed water. Therefore, a key enabling driver is the introduction of economic incentives to reduce the cost of reclaimed water and make it competitive with well water. The price of reclaimed water is not competitive against pumping well water. In Malaga (region of Andalusia) well water costs approximately €0.05/m³, whereas reclaimed water is priced at €0.12/m³, making the latter highly uncompetitive. Thus, a key enabling driver is changes in water tariffs or municipal support to finance the costs to reduce the price for reclaimed water.

Furthermore, the Axarquía pilot region faces challenges related to the discharge of secondary treated water into marine environments, leading to aquatic pollution. Based on insights from the region, taxes of discharging wastewater to the sea are relatively small, while the exact amounts of nutrients are not quantified. Therefore, a key enabling driver is to adapt discharge taxes to reflect the environmental costs caused by nutrient pollution.

Additionally, the lack of piping infrastructure to support the use of reclaimed water further hinders its adoption. To enable farmers to use reclaimed water solutions for irrigation purposes, extensive infrastructure upgrades are required. The current distribution network is not designed for large-scale reclaimed water usage, meaning that major investments in pipelines and treatment plants are necessary to allow all farmers the option of using reclaimed water. On a positive note, such investments are currently undertaken by the regional governments of Spain as a part of their strategic plan to increase reclaimed water usage. However, more investments to upgrade the existing piping systems are also needed to prevent seawater intrusion, which negatively affects the salinity levels of the reclaimed water.

Specific governmental financial compensations include carbon and nitrogen credits, and price-subsidisation to support farmers in purchasing biobased fertilisers (also elaborated in D3.1) (Leflaive & Hjort, 2020) (Otoo et al., 2018).

Designated feed-in-tariff might also be a tool for bridging the price gap between conventional and circular solutions. A feed-in tariff is a policy mechanism that is typically used to promote renewable energy by ensuring producers receive a guaranteed price that is higher than the market rate for the energy they generate (Mendonça & Lacey, 2010). A feed-in tariff in the realm of reclaimed water and biobased fertilisers may ensure that the biobased fertilisers can reach a price-level, where the biobased fertilisers can compete with the mineral fertilisers. Further a feed-in tariff could stabilise the prices and create a demand-pull mechanism, similar to how feed-in tariffs have supported the renewable energy sector. A feed-in tariff can be set for a limited time period e.g. 10 years, or until biobased fertilisers are expected to be so well-established on the mainstream market.

Furthermore, economic incentives could help address the issue of freshwater consumption, which is particularly critical in Malaga, where extended droughts and

wide-reaching areas are prevalent. In this context, economic incentives could stimulate demand for alternative water sources and make circular solutions more competitive by aligning their prices with traditional fertilisers.

Besides levelling the price gap, all three pilots are facing significant barriers to scaling their circular solutions to reach competitive prices, because they need substantial investments. This creates a classic "chicken or egg" dilemma, large-scale implementation could reduce costs, but sufficient demand will not materialise until prices are competitive.

Summing up, across all three pilot regions, the common challenge is the difficulty of scaling and mainstreaming circular business models. These difficulties stem largely from price disadvantages and entrenched conventional industries, creating a lock in effect. Biobased fertilisers, for example, are not yet cost-competitive with mineral fertilisers, making it difficult for pilot projects to penetrate the mainstream market and gain a foothold in the fertiliser sector. To overcome these obstacles, substantial public funding is required. Public funding stands as a key enabling driver across all three pilots, as it facilitates investments in infrastructure, treatment facilities etc., and market competitiveness. Without targeted financial mechanisms such as subsidies, grants, and tariffs, the circular innovations risk stagnation before they can reach commercial viability.

6.1.3 Municipalities Fostering and Facilitating Collaboration Across Industries & Public Institutions

It is evident from all pilot regions that successful operation of circular nutrient value chains, to a much greater extent than linear systems for mineral fertilisers, relies on collaboration with public institutions such as municipalities.

Insights from the Gotland region illustrates that collaboration with the municipality is highly essential to create favourable local interpretations of EU legislation for private enterprises being allowed to undertake waste management practices. However, experience from the region has shown that waste- and wastewater collection practices are often separated into different municipal departments, which makes it even more difficult to collaborate with the right authorities. Thus, a key enabling driver is to break down silos within public institutions since decision-making of circular nutrient solution involves more municipal departments.

In the North German Plain region, collaboration with municipalities have been decisive to obtain the needed permissions to operate a composting facility. Without strong relationships and supportive individuals within local government, obtaining such approvals would have been significantly more difficult. Moreover, efforts to implement large-scale infrastructure changes—such as modifications to water pipelines and toilet systems—require coordination across multiple sectors, including architecture, urban planning, and public works, which adds to the complexity. Therefore, establishing relationships with local authorities is considered essential to drive such changes.

Similarly, in the Axarquía pilot region, collaboration with public authorities is key to increasing visibility and encouraging the uptake of reclaimed water. However, decisions related to water management are not exclusively made by municipalities. Sometimes the operator of the local WWTP can be a private entity or part of a private-public partnership. In addition, decisions related to upgrades of the piping infrastructure are often made by the regional government which increases complexity around collaboration given the variety of actors involved. Having a public water authority as one of the project partners illustrates how direct engagement with public institutions can support the rollout of tertiary treatment technologies and help scale reclaimed water production.

Municipalities and other public authorities can help ensure that the responsibility for collaboration does not fall solely on individual businesses and key individuals. This approach creates an environment conducive to innovation and resource sharing, enabling the development of circular value chains. By setting clear goals for nutrient recycling in the municipalities, the municipalities can create a shared vision that aligns the efforts of different stakeholders and actors involved in nutrient recycling. This can help to build legitimacy and trust that can further foster long-term dedication and partnerships

6.2 Market Drivers

Diving into the market drivers, the key enabling drivers identified across the three pilots are the fostering of:

- Increased awareness on water scarcity, soil degradation, and water reuse practices
- Implementation of third-party certifications or similar product assurance systems
- Increased commercial focus on environmental responsibility in products and raising public awareness on environmental challenges in the current system

All three pilot regions involve small, innovative start-ups offering alternative products to those dominating the traditional, linear market. A key challenge for these pilots is entering a well-established market, largely driven by long-standing practices. Their current scale is insufficient to supply large agricultural fields, while conventional solutions benefit from existing infrastructure, legal frameworks, and consumer habits, making it harder for circular business models to gain traction.

6.2.1 Increasing Awareness

The perceptions of biobased fertilisers and end-products based on human sanitary waste pose as a barrier for adoption of circular nutrient practices, while increased awareness of environmental externalities from traditional wastewater practices represent a key enabling driver for adoption and scaling of nutrient recycling. A recurring concern expressed by the pilot regions is how consumers perceive and act towards purchasing products grown with recycled nutrients and reclaimed water. This is

especially relevant in relation to food producers, who might not be willing to risk reputation.

For all three pilot regions, educating and engaging the public on the safety of biobased fertiliser, water scarcity, environmental pollution, and the broader benefits of supporting products that contribute to water and nutrient recycling systems is a key enabling driver to change negative perceptions around the offerings.

Education and promotion are crucial for building trust and advancing nutrient recycling solutions. Public awareness can be fostered through campaigns, events, media coverage, and integration into school curricula. These efforts could be supported by environmental organisations, government agencies, industries, and other relevant stakeholders, serving as a key enabling driver to create a demand-pull mechanism for circular products.

Lack of understanding and awareness can potentially limit the perceived value of the circular solutions and collaborations in the pilot regions. For instance, it is highlighted that the general society of the Gotland region are not aware about the amount of phosphorus and nitrogen released into the sea. They are accustomed to the 'flush and forget' concept and might assume that the WWTP remove all pollutants before releasing treated wastewater into ecosystems. The same issues are evident in the North German Plain region, highlighting that the broader society primarily focus on CO₂.

In both Gotland and the North German Plain regions, festivals could serve as platforms establish public awareness campaigns and educate visitors on the benefits of recycling human sanitary waste. They further possess the potential to drive the social acceptance of unisex urinals, which are important to increase the scales of urine able to be collected. Festivals, with their novelty and openness to new experiences, provide an ideal setting for such initiatives (van Vliet, 2021). In addition, the North German Plain faces challenges to market expansions in countries with no experience of using liquid fertilisers. This increases the importance of educating consumers on best-practices when using liquid fertilisers.

In the Axarquia pilot region, education must be targeted at both farmers and end-consumers. While social acceptance has started to occur related to the use of reclaimed water due to extreme weather conditions, some farmers are still reluctant on its use. Education is important in this relation to change the mentality into reclaimed water being a necessity to reduce water scarcity, however, with salinity posing as a major influencer on farmer-perceptions, a key enabling driver is to showcase successful methods to bring down salinity levels. For end-consumers, education on the benefits of reclaimed water is highly essential to reduce biased perceptions and potential scepticism, thus driving the adoption of fruits grown from reclaimed water. However, consumers are often not aware of the use of reclaimed water which calls for third-party certifications.

6.2.2 Third-party Certifications or Similar Product Assurance Systems

The adoption of biobased fertilisers faces notable challenges related to social acceptance across all three pilot regions. To address this issue the development of suitable certification schemes is identified as a key enabling driver. It would not only ensure the safe use of such fertilisers but also enhance public trust, thereby stimulating market demand. This perspective is reinforced by De Boer et al. (2018), who highlight the potential of certification to improve the perceived environmental and health safety of eco-fertilisers, ultimately strengthening their market position.

In the Gotland region, potential certification schemes encompass both festival-related and fertiliser-related certifications. Regarding festivals, it is highlighted that a 'green certification' could help stimulate demand from festivals for more environmentally friendly sanitation services, thereby increasing interest in solutions that enable nutrient recycling. In parallel, certifications of the fertiliser itself are crucial to ensure its safety, which may enhance farmers' and crop buyers' willingness to adopt its use. Furthermore, certification of the fertiliser can serve as a communication tool targeting consumers by emphasising the product's environmental benefits. In context of the Gotland region, a suitable and fitting certification is currently investigated. The KRAV¹ certification has been identified as a potential avenue, provided that the fertiliser meets the criteria defined by this standard.

For the North German Plain, a similar certification is considered beneficial, however, legal permissions are needed before entering this stage. Nevertheless, integration with third-party certifications for buildings such as BREEAM² can contribute to stimulate demand for installation of urine treatment technologies among building owners.

In the Axarquia pilot region, an official certification of the end-products grown with reclaimed water to highlight its reduced environmental impact. Currently, most certifications do not take the origin of the water into account meaning that the use of reclaimed water will not be visible for end-consumers. Current certification schemes and labels do not fully capture the use of reclaimed water meaning that development of certification for the products based on CE principles is needed to increase the value of

¹ The KRAV Standards comply with the EU regulation for organic production, which is a requirement for all production and sales of organic goods within the EU. However, KRAV goes further with stricter standards for animal welfare, environment and health, climate, and better working conditions (KRAV n.d.)

² Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method (BREEAM) is a certification system used to specify and measure the sustainability performance of buildings, helping to meet sustainability goals over time (BREEAM 2025)

the fruits. However, private certification schemes such as GLOBALG.A.P.³, LEAF Marque⁴, or organic labels are relevant to investigate in this context.

In order to achieve social acceptance and credibility among the end-consumers in the respective regions, third-party certification is a widely used tool to counter such perceptions. Certifications ensuring the quality and effectiveness of biobased fertilisers, whether derived from reclaimed wastewater, urine, or faeces, can help stimulate demand for crops grown with reclaimed water by fostering greater trust between nutrient recycling fertiliser companies and farmers. These mechanisms can help verify that biobased fertilisers comply with health, environmental, and agricultural standards, while addressing potential concerns related to contamination, nutrient consistency, and public acceptance. Without clear safety assurances, market adoption may be hindered, preventing these circular solutions from scaling effectively.

6.2.3 Increased Commercial Focus on Environmental Responsibility in Products

The last key enabling driver relates to environmental responsibility. The rising environmental responsibility among potential customers is driving the demand for circular products and technologies, which is in favour of the pilots and their businesses.

Experience from the Gotland region has shown that an increased focus on reducing climate impact among potential customers has generated interest in implementing urine recycling technologies. At the same time, it is highlighted to be easier to convince organisations, particularly those with an environmental focus, to adopt more environmentally friendly agricultural practices. In this context, another key enabling driver is the growing interest from major players in the food industry who wish to market products grown using biobased fertilisers. For instance, Spendroops is a significant actor in the beverage market, and its influence can play a pivotal role in encouraging farmers to adopt such fertilisers.

In the case of the North German Plain, the increasing emphasis on Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) requirements also serves as a driver for adopting technologies or products that help reduce environmental footprints. Thus, the growing awareness of sustainability and corporate responsibility functions as a key enabling driver for motivating businesses to adopt eco-friendly practices. This applies both to building owners considering the installation of technology to reduce their environmental impact, and notably to food retailers. For instance, preliminary discussions have already

³ GLOBALG.A.P. standards are designed to foster the global adoption of more responsible farming practices. Audits are conducted using methods such as reviewing documentation, conducting interviews, and performing on-site observations. When the criteria are fulfilled, the producer or producer group is awarded certification (GlobalG.A.P. n.d.)

⁴ LEAF Marque certification builds on the principles of Integrated Farm Management (IFM) – a whole farm approach utilizing modern technology and traditional methods to deliver prosperous farming enriching the environment and engaging the local communities (LEAF n.d.)

been initiated with a major retailer seeking to lower its Scope 3 emissions across its supply chain, an ambition that the use of this type of fertiliser could support.

Similarly, in the Axarquia pilot region, some retailers are requesting sustainability data on the fruits they source. Overall, this underlines that heightened attention to environmental impact within the value chain is a key enabling driver with the potential to positively influence demand for circular nutrient recycling solutions.

6.3 Operational and Organisational Drivers

Diving into the operational and organisational drivers, the key enabling drivers identified across the three pilots' concerns:

- Development of adaptable product offerings
- Maturing technology (R&D) and atomising processes
- Expanding capacity and partnerships
- Leveraging key individuals

6.3.1 Developing Adaptable Product Offerings

Given that the three pilots rely on farmers, a group traditionally known for its conservative approach, a key enabling driver is the need to develop adaptable product offerings that align with existing farming practices while clearly demonstrating the benefits of these new solutions. A prime example of this is the technology used in the Axarquia pilot project, which enhances nutrient levels for specific crops by combining irrigation with a SFT to monitor crop's needs for water and nutrients. This technology not only optimises nutrient application but also encourages the adoption of nutrient-rich reclaimed water by showcasing the tangible benefits of the technologies involved. This challenge is also present in the North German Plain and Gotland region, where the biobased fertilisers hold potential benefits for farmers. However, the current production capacities of these pilot regions are insufficient to meet the demand of farmers, complicating the foundation of the business models underlying the circular value chains.

For all three pilot regions, developing adaptable products that integrate seamlessly into existing farming practices is essential for ensuring the adoption of new biobased fertilisers. This is a critical factor in establishing a sustainable business foundation for the pilots. The shared vision of future-proofing a continuous demand for biobased fertilisers at scale drives the businesses to further develop and improve their solutions.

6.3.2 Maturing Technology (R&D)

Across the three pilot regions, it is emphasised that their respective technologies require further development through R&D to enable scalability and ensure competitiveness with mineral fertiliser practices. The pilot regions recognise that their solutions still need significant advancements to meet the demands of the agricultural sector. Specifically, the nutrient recycling technologies must reach a level of reliability comparable to traditional fertiliser methods in order to overcome hesitation and reluctance among

farmers. For instance, in the Axarquia pilot region it also involves that the SFT will be able to measure nutrient levels in different crop types.

As mentioned previously, achieving economies of scale is critical for improving the cost-competitiveness of these products. By increasing production capacity, the pilot regions will be better positioned to offer affordable alternatives to mineral fertilisers, which are currently more established in the market. Reaching sufficient scales is highly essential across the North German Plain and Gotland region and a key challenge remains: the pilots are unable to meet the volume requirements necessary to attract and retain the interest of farmers on a large scale. Greater automation of processes will allow the business models to reduce their reliance on costly personnel, which in turn will help improve the cost competitiveness of the products.

6.3.3 Expanding Capacity and Partnerships

Scaling operations to meet future demands is critical to the long-term success of circular businesses. The pilot regions universally emphasise the need for strategic partnerships to enable the successful scaling of technologies.

A key enabling driver for successful value chain collaboration is the clear definition of roles and the enhancement of mutual understanding among value chain actors. As highlighted in the Gotland region, it is essential that responsibilities are clearly determined and that all actors reach a shared agreement on 'who does what'. Similarly, findings from the Axarquia pilot region indicate that collaboration is strengthened when each actor gains knowledge about the needs of the others in the circular partnership. In this way, a deeper understanding of each actor's role and organisational needs enables more effective structuring of the value chain, ultimately enhancing overall performance.

Moreover, beneficial partnerships are a key enabler of capacity expansion and adoption rate. For instance, in the Axarquia pilot region, the collaboration between technology providers, with fertigation solutions, and a farming cooperative, with an extensive network of farmers, exemplifies how strategic partnerships are valuable for future scaling of the technologies.

For the North German Plain, partnerships with local farmers' associations or relevant agricultural chambers are particularly desirable. These associations play a vital role in bundling the services farmers need, and the agricultural chambers perform knowledge transfers with consultants conducting workshops and training for farmers, while also possessing certification power. Consequently, partnerships with associations that directly connect the pilot regions to their target segments are seen as crucial for future progress.

In conclusion, a key enabling driver across all three pilots is the necessity of expanding capacity and forming strategic partnerships to scale operations and ensure the success of new technologies.

6.3.4 Leveraging Key Individuals

In all pilot regions, key individuals play a critical role in driving operational efficiency and innovation and are essential to the success of circular value chain and the business models. These individuals are pivotal in advancing projects, fostering collaboration, and ensuring the achievement of goals. They envision the project's potential, inspire others, and maintain momentum by advocating for the cause and ensuring it stays a priority.

In all pilot regions, key individuals have been instrumental in coordinating efforts, setting up meetings and securing communication among the partners in the circular value chains. Especially in the Axarquia pilot region, regular meetings and clear communication channels have enhanced collaboration and aligned efforts for improved knowledge sharing, ultimately strengthening the partnership.

These key individuals excel at overcoming challenges, whether technical, regulatory, or organisational, through problem-solving and persistence. They promote broader participation and shared responsibility, enabling the creation of circular value chains, which rely more heavily on collaboration than traditional linear value chains.

As agents of change, they challenge the status quo and push for the adoption of new practices. Their influence shifts mindsets towards more sustainable and innovative approaches. Within the circular value chain, their role is indispensable, driving the project forward and ensuring seamless collaboration across the entire value chain for successful outcomes.

7 Perspectives Outside P2Green Pilot Regions

7.1 Common and General Perspectives Across EU

The analysis of the key enabling drivers across the P2Green pilot regions has generated valuable insights that extend beyond local contexts and offer broader relevance for organisations across the EU. These stakeholders may include legislative bodies, municipalities, WWTPs, companies, and other entities involved in or supporting nutrient recycling value chains.

One of the most crucial enabling drivers for establishing a successful circular business model and nutrient recycling is the legislative landscape. Laws and regulations can either foster or hinder the development of nutrient recycling businesses. Across the three pilot regions, it is evident that the current regulatory framework is fragmented, with varying interpretations at European, national and regional levels.

Rather than acting as a barrier, legislation must evolve to enable innovation, particularly for start-ups and small and medium enterprises (SMEs) working with circular solutions. Legislative measures should also address freshwater scarcity, incentivising water reuse and supporting the transition to more sustainable and circular alternatives.

Additionally, governmental and supra-governmental bodies must actively legitimise the use of human-derived nutrients to address ongoing societal concerns. Public acceptance remains a critical hurdle for broader adoption of circular fertilisers, and government-led normalisation and communication efforts are key to overcoming it.

Ensuring that circular products meet market demand is another important factor for a successful implementation. Nutrient recycling solutions must be adaptable to diverse agricultural, and irrigation needs, beyond current crops like barley, mangoes, and avocados. Certification schemes guaranteeing the safety and quality of recycled fertilisers and water are essential for building trust among end-users and industry stakeholders.

In terms of operational management, the pilot regions highlight the importance of strong partnerships within circular value chains. Collaboration among public institutions, private companies, and research organisations facilitates knowledge exchange, skills development, and process optimisation. These partnerships not only enhance operational efficiency but also contribute to building resilient, long-term business ecosystems.

Equally important are key individuals who act as driving forces within these initiatives. Their vision, dedication, and ability to connect stakeholders are vital in sustaining momentum and ensuring the initiatives move forward.

Examining the three pilot regions, it became clear that a key enabling driver and also a common barrier across the project pilots that a currently hindering the upscaling of the businesses, was the need for substantial capital investment. Early-stage innovations

often face difficulties in securing funding due to perceived risks. As a result, public funding and government-backed financial mechanisms are essential to bridge this gap.

Finally, the commercial viability of biobased fertilisers depends on achieving economies of scale. Current high production costs and low market demand create a classic “chicken-and-egg” scenario. Without sufficient scale, prices remain high; without competitive pricing, demand stays low. External financial support is therefore indispensable for progressing toward commercialisation.

8 Conclusion

This report has set out to investigate and identify the common key enabling drivers present within the circular value chains established by the three P2Green pilot regions. In doing so, it has also examined the new collaborative constellations that emerge within circular business models—partnerships that are essential to transforming waste into a resource and reintegrating it into nutrient cycles.

The analysis was structured around three overarching categories of drivers: (1) the systematic and regulatory drivers, (2) the market drivers, and finally (3) the organisational and operational drivers. Across all pilot regions, a shared challenge is the difficulty of commercialising circular solutions and entering mainstream markets. The conventional industries such as the WWTPs, the fertiliser companies, and the agricultural industry are deeply embedded in a traditional linear system, creating significant barriers to innovation and new market entrants.

Under systematic and regulatory drivers, several key enabling conditions emerged. Firstly, supportive regulatory environments are critical. Governments must create policies and legal frameworks that allow for the development and maturation of circular technologies and business models, particularly by small and innovative companies. Secondly, harmonisation of fragmented legislation across EU, national, and regional levels is necessary to enhance the attractiveness of biobased fertilisers. This includes reforming water use policies that currently incentivise overconsumption of freshwater and well water. Thirdly, governmental financial support is essential to overcome the price gap between circular and mineral fertilisers. Here, mechanisms such as dedicated tariffs could play a key role in levelling the playing field.

The need for significant infrastructure investments emerged as another systemic barrier to scale. Without access to capital for treatment facilities and processing technologies, many innovations risk stagnation before they can be scaled. Third-party certification is another key enabling driver among the pilots. When promoting nutrient recycling, social acceptance needs to be addressed, which can be done by introducing third-party certification. Certifications are widely used and can help verify that biobased fertilisers meet health, environmental, and agricultural standards, while addressing potential concerns related to contamination, nutrient consistency, and public acceptance. Municipalities play a unique enabling role by fostering cross-sector collaboration between public institutions, industries, and researchers. They can facilitate knowledge exchange, reduce regulatory burdens for individual actors, and support the formation of robust circular ecosystems.

Investigating the market drivers across the pilots, revealed that the key enabling drivers within this category was divided into (1) increasing awareness, (2) price competitiveness, and (3) environmental responsibility. An increasing public awareness and acceptance of water and nutrient recycling is key. Education, transparency, and trust-building are essential to generating demand-pull for circular products. Price

competitiveness remains a prerequisite for wider adoption, again requiring initial public investment to enable scale. Lastly, a greater focus on more sustainable practices and CO₂-reduction targets are strengthening the case for nutrient recycling, aligning well with industry and policy ambitions for greener production systems.

On the organisational and operational front, four common enabling drivers emerged: (1) development of adaptable product offerings, (2) maturing technology, (3) expanded partnerships and capacity, and (4) the presence of key individuals. Circular products and solutions must fit seamlessly into existing farming and irrigation practices. Given the conservative nature of the agricultural sector, the pilots must demonstrate clear improvements in yields and resource efficiency to gain farmers' trust. Another key driver is maturing the technology to ensure reliability and scalability. The pilots emphasise that achieving technological maturity is crucial for gaining acceptance and competing with mineral fertilisers. Expanding capacity and forming strategic partnerships is equally critical. Collaborations with farmer associations, research institutions, and business networks can help the pilots access new knowledge and market opportunities. Finally, leveraging key individuals has proven essential across all pilots. These individuals play a central role in driving innovation, fostering collaboration, and overcoming regulatory and technical challenges.

The analysis of the three pilot regions clearly demonstrates that the enabling drivers for circular value chains differ fundamentally from those underpinning traditional linear systems. Circular models require robust cross-sector collaboration, continuous technological innovation, and a supportive policy framework. In particular, policymakers play a pivotal role in unlocking market potential by addressing economic barriers and establishing regulatory conditions that nurture and accelerate circular entrepreneurship.

To challenge the status quo and transition towards a more CE, political support is necessary to push solutions that may not yet be market competitive but hold significant societal value. However, this transition cannot rely on isolated efforts; it requires a holistic approach where regulatory frameworks, innovation, and cross-sector collaboration go hand in hand.

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